

Analysis of Factors Affecting Wardah Cosmetics Purchase Interest, Case Study on Consumers of Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia

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ABSTRACT : This research is entitled Analysis of Factors Affecting Wardah Cosmetics Purchase Interest, Case Study on Consumers of Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia. The object of this research is product quality, brand image, celebrity endorser and buying interest in Wardah cosmetics on Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia consumers. The population in this study were people who were interested in buying Wardah cosmetics at Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia, with a sample of 106 respondents. The sampling technique used was accidental sampling. Analysis of the data in this study using multiple linear regression and testing for hypotheses using the t test. For testing the hypothesis in this study, the results showed that product quality had a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics, brand image had a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics and celebrity endorsers had a negative and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics.

KEYWORDS -product quality, brand image, celebrity endorser and buying interest

I. INTRODUCTION

Looking charming and attractive is the dream of all women, not even a few of them are willing to spend some of their money just to buy a product that can be used as a beauty support. One of the products that can support beauty is cosmetics. Currently, cosmetics have become a major need for some women in supporting their popularity because beauty is an asset that must be maintained by every woman so that she is always attractive. Not only that, looking charming and attractive can increase a woman's self-confidence in front of many people. In an effort to meet the need to support their beauty, women certainly want to choose cosmetic products that they think can provide satisfaction when used, so manufacturers must continue to innovate in order to win the competition in the cosmetic industry.

Competition in the cosmetic industry today continues to be tight, for that matter that must be considered for manufacturers in order to compete is to recognize what aspects can affect a person's attention or interest in making a purchase, because before they decide to buy a product, of course they They want to think about and make sure the product they want to buy is indeed suitable for what they need. Buying interest is an attitude that arises in a person in response to an object that displays a willingness to make a purchase (Kotler and Keller 2009).

The product being marketed is a very important weapon in winning the competition if it has great quality or quality. Conversely, low-quality products are difficult to get an image from consumers. Therefore, the resulting product must always be of good quality (Indriyo, 2000).

Another factor that is thought to be able to influence buying interest is brand image or brand image (Arifin, 2015). Brand image is a person's perception of a brand that is based on the good or bad of the brand that is in

one's mind, brand image is a belief that has been formed in one's mind about a product that has been felt. Research on brand image or brand image was conducted by Salfina and Gusri (2018) with research results showing that brand image has a positive effect on buying interest.

Celebrity endorser is also one of the factors that also influence the emergence of buying interest in someone to make a buyer. Celebrity endorser is an actor or artist, entertainer or athlete who is known or publicly known for his success in their respective fields to support an advertised product (Shimp, 2010). Research on celebrity endorsers was conducted by Ningsih (2019) and showed the results that there was a positive influence of celebrity endorsers on buying interest.

This research focuses on cosmetic brands from PT. Paragon Technology and Innovation, namely Wardah, because Wardah has been widely recognized in various circles of society with its halal label which makes it different from other cosmetics. This is evidenced in 2013 WardahKosmetik received the International Halal Award from the Word Halal Council as a pioneer of halal cosmetics in the world. Wardah is one of the local cosmetic brands produced by PT. Paragon Technology and Innovation, which was first created in 1995 with cosmetic products that are safe, halal and practical to meet the needs and tastes of consumers, especially Indonesian women. Wardah always maintains product quality, based on strong manufacturing, so that Wardah is always a mainstay in cosmetic and skin care products that are created completely and safely.

Cosmetics from the Wardah brand have spread in almost all regions in Indonesia, so the researchers focused this research on Wardah consumers at Wardah Rita Cosmetic Outlets Supermall Purwokerto. Rita Supermall Purwokerto was chosen as the object of research because Rita Supermall is the first mall that is present in the city of Purwokerto and is located in the city center as well as being in a busy city area because it is located in front of the Purwokerto Indonesia square.

Based on the results of pre-observation conducted by researchers through initial interviews with one of the sales promotion girl (SPG) at the Wardah Rita Supermall Purwokerto outlet, it was found that there were problems regarding the purchase of Wardah cosmetics, namely uneven sales levels. There is a very high difference between the turnover of Wardah cosmetic products in the last 6 months, namely from June to November 2020. Statistical data on company sales cannot be shared in general, but in the interview it was explained that the difference occurred due to the high level of sales of lipstick products that were not matched. with other products. Almost half of the sales turnover is dominated by lipstick products, which is 40%. While the remaining 60% are other products, namely powder, foundation, eyeshadow, blush, eyebrow concealer, eye liner, mascara, and highlighter. The lowest turnover is highlighter products with a percentage of 5%. The difference between the highest turnover and the lowest turnover is quite significant, so it is necessary to conduct research on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics so that it can be known with certainty what causes the inequality of these purchases.

II. RESEARCH METHODE

The type of research conducted in this research is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research is defined as a research method or method based on the philosophy of positivism, which is usually used for research on certain populations or samples, how to obtain data by using research instruments, the results of data analysis are quantitative statistics, and aim to perform hypothesis testing which has been determined previously. The object of this research is buying interest, product quality, brand image, and celebrity endorser at Wardah Cosmetics at the Rita Supermall Outlet Purwokerto Indonesia.

The population in this study were women who had used Wardah cosmetics. The number of population in this study is infinite because the number of people who are interested in making purchases of Wardah cosmetics at the Wardah Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia outlet is not known for certain or is said to be infinite. Because the population in this study is unknown, the maximum p value (1-p) is 0.25. The sample size when using a 95% confidence level with an error rate of not more than 10% is 96.04. Researchers determined to take a sample of 106 people using accidental sampling technique.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1). The Influence of Product Quality on Buying Interest

The quality of Wardah cosmetic products according to respondents at Wardah Rita Supermall PurwokertoIndonesiacosmetic outlets is good, because the results of respondents' answers show that 0.47% answered strongly disagree and 3.54% answered disagree. 6.84% answered neutral, 38.91% answered agree and 50.23% answered strongly agree. This indicates that the response from respondents to Wardah cosmetics where Wardah is a cosmetic with the ability to be easy to use, has reliability or progress, has specifications that match the description on the packaging and has good durability.

Based on the results of the answers from all respondents, it is known that the most answers are the answers to the 3rd statement which states that wardah is a cosmetic that is safe to use. This means that people are interested in making purchases of Wardah cosmetics because they think that Wardah is a cosmetic that is safe to use. According to Tjiptono (2010), product quality includes an effort to fulfill the expectations that already exist in a person's mind for a product. Product quality is a must-have for every company so that they are able to compete in the market and can give a satisfying impression while meeting the needs and desires of consumers. The better the level of quality of a given product, the greater the level of satisfaction felt by consumers. Therefore, the increase or decrease that occurs in product quality can affect buying interest. Based on the results of the t test, it can be seen that product quality has a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics at Wardah cosmetics outlets at Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia. This is evidenced by the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($4.728 > 1.659$) and significance ($0.000 < 0.05$).

2). The Influence of Brand Image on Buying Interest

The image of Wardah cosmetics on respondents at Wardah Rita Supermall PurwokertoIndonesiacosmetic outlets is good, because the results of respondents' answers show that 1.18% answered strongly disagree, 2.12% answered disagree, 10.61% answered neutral, 41.27% answered agree and 44.81% answered strongly agree. This indicates that respondents have a positive view of Wardah cosmetics because cosmetics from the Wardahbrand are well known, have a good reputation, have their own charm when compared to other cosmetics and can attract consumers' attention to remain loyal in using cosmetics with the Wardah brand.

Based on the respondents' overall answers to the brand image variable, it can be seen that the highest answer is the third statement or item which states that Wardah consumers at the Wardah Rita Supermall PurwokertoIndonesiacosmetic outlet considers cosmetics with the Wardah brand to have its own charm when compared to other brands. This is because Wardah does have a good image based on halal labeling which is not widely owned by other brands, of course this can increase buying interest in Wardah cosmetics.

Brand image is a collection of associations with a particular brand that has been embedded in the minds or memories of everyone. Bringing up a good image or impression on a product, of course, will be very meaningful for marketers, because a product with a good image will affect brand assessment. The image of a brand that has been assessed positively will certainly be easier for consumers to remember. Products that have been impressed with a positive image will certainly have an effect on increasing one's trust in the brand. The higher a person's level of trust in a brand, the more influential it will be in an effort to increase buying interest in the brand.

The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Rahman and Abir (2020), which suggests that brand image has a positive and significant effect on buying interest. Based on the results of the t test, it can be seen that brand image has a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics at Wardah cosmetics outlets at Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia. This is evidenced by t_{count} brand image $> t_{table}$ ($5.544 > 1.659$) and significance ($0.000 < 0.05$).

3). The Influence of Celebrity Endorsers on Buying Interest

According to Shimp (2003), celebrity endorser is the use of celebrities as stars in advertising through various media ranging from print, social media, or television advertising. Judging from the results of the tabulation of respondents' answers to Wardah cosmetics at the Wardah Rita Supermall Outlet Purwokerto Indonesia, the lowest answer is the first statement which states that the celebrity who stars in Wardah cosmetic products is a

celebrity who is less recognized by respondents, therefore consumers of Wardah cosmetics does not consider the celebrity endorser chosen to promote Wardah cosmetics when they want to make a purchase.

If an endorser has been trusted by the audience, it is likely that the message they convey will be well received and can increase buying interest in the advertised product, and vice versa, the message conveyed by an endorser who seems dubious may be rejected or not received properly. by the audience because the audience cannot understand the content of the message to be conveyed by the celebrity so they are not interested in making a purchase.

Based on the results of the t test, it can be seen that celebrity endorsers have a negative and significant effect on buying interest in Wardah cosmetics at Wardah cosmetic outlets at Rita Supermall Purwokerto Indonesia. This is evidenced by the celebrity endorser tcount<ttable (-2.167 < 1.659) and the significance (0.033 < 0.05).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1). Conclusions

The first hypothesis which states that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention is accepted. This is evident from the value of tcount greater than ttable (4.728 > 1.659) and significance (0.000 < 0.05). This shows that with good product quality it will increase consumer buying interest. The second hypothesis which states that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention is accepted. This is evident from the value of tcount greater than ttable (5.544 > 1.659) and significance (0.000 < 0.05). With these results, it means that the better the brand image, the more consumers buy interest. The third hypothesis, which states that celebrity endorsers have a positive and significant effect on buying interest, is rejected. This is evident from the value of tcount smaller than ttable (-2.167 < 1.659) and the significance (0.033 < 0.05). This implies that consumers in making purchases do not see who the celebrity is promoting the product.

The company is expected to improve the quality of each product, especially in terms of durability. Good quality products are products with long durability capabilities. Companies should maintain the image that has been built, namely halal-certified cosmetics and continue to advertise their products so that they are always known among the public. The choice of celebrity endorser must be considered, it is better if the celebrity used is a celebrity who has its own charm, especially in terms of physicality so that it can create a distinct impression for consumers to make a purchase.

2) Suggestions

The company is expected to improve the quality of each product, especially in terms of durability. Good quality products are products with long durability capabilities. Companies should maintain the image that has been built, namely halal-certified cosmetics and continue to advertise their products so that they are always known among the public.

The choice of celebrity endorser must be considered, it is better if the celebrity used is a celebrity who has its own charm, especially in terms of physicality so that it can create a distinct impression for consumers to make a purchase. In order to obtain a better research model supported by a very strong theory, it is recommended that more references to research are considered capable and supportive according to the topic to be studied.

The number of respondents is only 106 people, it would be better if the number of samples was taken with a larger number in order to better describe the actual field conditions. It is hoped that other variables outside of this research can be added that can affect buying interest such as price, location, promotion, people, process and other variables.

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